

IMPACT OF WORK STRESS AND PROFESSIONAL BURNOUT ON EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION AMONG IT PROFESSIONALS

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Abstract: In today's competitive world Information technology sector is developing day by day that is featured by long working hours, prolonged screen time, continuous client service, rapid technological innovations all these contribute to dominate work stress and professional job out among employees. As a result of these stressors the employees are unable to balance their professional and personal life that ultimately lead to conflict in their personal life. The study analyses the impact of work stress and burn out on employee Job satisfaction which will adversely affect the organisation sustainability. The study also aims to examine the relationship between the variables and determine how they are collectively influence employee Job satisfaction and performance. Data for the study were collected through structure questionnaire that measures the factors affecting the work-related stress and employee satisfaction. The findings indicate an adverse relationship between the work stress and job satisfaction shows that higher levels of work stress and burn out will lead to decreased satisfaction at work. The study concludes the need for effective stress management measures, support systems and well-being initiatives to improve job satisfaction.

Keywords: IT Professional, Work stress, professional burn out, Job satisfaction, employee well being.

I. INTRODUCTION

Information technology sector has transformed the real work places that create the work environments monitored by strict and tight deadlines, continuous innovation and create more competition. In spite of all this IT sector offers huge career growth opportunities and monetary benefits which give rise to the IT employees work related issues. Prolonged working hours, complex project deadlines, role clarity and all those technological changes will lead to immense pressure to the IT professionals. It not only affects the Job performance but also the psychological well-being which leads to a critical issue for the sustainability of the organisation and work force. Professional burnout which is often a psychological syndrome developed by Christina Maslach. It is one major issue faced by most of the employees which is characterized by emotional exhaustion, depression and a state of reduction in the personal accomplishment. Due to the project deadline cycles and high-performance expectations in the IT sector these Job burn out will gradually take away the employees' commitment, motivation, innovative skills and engagement. When these stress level increases it affects the employee mental health, productivity and also disrupts the team collaboration and performance of the firm.

Employee job satisfaction is one which determines the well-being and effectiveness of the organisation which they get satisfaction and they can easily adjust with their current roles. Giving more important to this matter help an organisation effective stress management strategy, promotion of employee wellbeing both mentally and physically and increase job satisfaction. In this demanding nature of the IT professionals it is very essential to study the stress level and job satisfaction.

High levels of stress and burnout can negatively influence job satisfaction, leading to absenteeism, reduced productivity, increased turnover intention, and poor organizational morale. In the IT sector, where human capital is the most valuable asset, maintaining employee well-being is essential for sustaining innovation and competitiveness. As the organisation labour force is very important in their organisation's productivity, every organisations success depend upon the human force .so it is the duty of the management to make necessary arrangements to minimise those stress level problems and suffocation faced by the employees in their work place. Then only the organisation will achieve its heights. The main focus is to understand the extent to which these work-related stresses will affect the job satisfaction among IT employees and valuable insights for improving workplace strategies in the IT Industry

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

IT sector has been undergoing unpredictable changes in terms of new policies and emerging technology that created a stressful environment to the employees. Due to these globalisations the IT sector is compelled to adjust with the work environment. This tech upgradation has completely reversed the work patterns of employees and made it an inevitable to deduct the workforce in the work sector. All these changes have affected the societal economic and mental well-being of the employees working in this sector. The IT Industry is focussed by technological changes like continuous hours of work, project expectations, team work and continuous skill upgradation process. Prolonged focus to all these stress lead to job burn out which will result in mental and physical imbalances. Sometimes it may affect to the employee productivity and job satisfaction. In a prominent industry like Information Technology understanding how these factors will become important is a very serious issue. Most of the organisations give priority to productivity and performance output often go above the psychological well-being of the employees. This result in creating an ineffective human resource and higher the turnover retention rates. Therefore, it is very essential to investigate the extent to which these work place stress and burn out will negatively affect employee job satisfaction in the IT sector and also to understand the strategies that the organisations can adopt to increase the employee well-being and effectiveness of the organisation.

III. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Now a days IT industry has created a "pressure cooker environment" which is mainly focussed on endless deadlines, 24 hours connectivity options, and also the need to innovate the skills that meet the needs of the present scenario. While the industry offers huge monetary rewards the mental well-being of the professional is insignificant. The issue really is the increasing level of stress deviating from different roles, excessive workload and the "always on" culture lead to professional burnout. When the IT employees reach this immense stage the passion for technology often turns to cynicism and detachment. This shift increases the psychological well-being which demands professional efficacy and mental health. The decline of these well-being led to decreased job satisfaction across the industry. For those organisations that gives high salary, perks and incentives these chronic situations sometimes result in lack of accomplishment and a desire to exit the profession entirely. So, there is a pressing need to examine how these stressors interact as retention strategies often fail to address the mentioned professional and psychological burnout that makes daily tasks very difficult.

IV. RESEARCH GAP

Despite of several research on work related stress, job burnout and employee job satisfaction there exists only a limited variable interaction with these factors related to IT employees. Many previous studies are conducted on the work-related stress on nurses, bank employees, teachers but a very few studies were conducted on the basic variables like occupational stress and burnout on IT professionals. Also, the research is not updated after post pandemic situations which includes hybrid and work from home which adversely influence employee stress level and satisfaction. Moreover, insufficient attention has been given to factors like organisational support, work life balance in shaping employee well-being both physically and mentally. Therefore, there is a need for the research that focus on these variables in the contemporary IT Industry.

V. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the key factors affecting professional burnout experienced by IT employees
- To analyse the relationship between Job burnout and employee retention among IT employees
- To study the impact of work-related pressure on Job satisfaction among IT employees

VI. LITERATURE REVIEW

Linga Yulianna.et.al (2025) found that work stress and job burnout positively affect the employees to leave the organisation. The findings of the study show that the employee having higher level of stress compel them to leave the organisation. But Job burn out did not show that much influence on the employee retention strategies. The study concludes that those organisations that works in high pressure must prioritize to manage work related stress to reduce the employee turnover. Also, they emphasize the importance of supporting work strategies that will promote mental well-being and foster work life balance.

Dr.Usman Mohideen KS and Sabarish A(2024)in their study examine the major factors that affects the Stress level of IT professional and the effectiveness of stress management strategies. The objective of the study is to find out the main stressors like workload, technological changes, role change and analyse the impact of these factors on employee job satisfaction. The findings show that IT professionals experience more stress with their workload than any other profession and also the technological advancements shows a positive relation with these work stress. The authors suggest that the organisation should give more priority to their mental health and provide supportive work environment to increase the employee Job satisfaction.

Dr.V Karthikeyan and Dr S Malathi(2022) in their study analyses the impact of work stress on job satisfaction among IT employees. The main aim of the study is to examine the work stress and job satisfaction experienced by the IT employees. The findings show that the stress arising from long hours of work, multitasking, project deadlines will adversely affect the work and employee job satisfaction. The authors suggest that the It sector must implement effective stress management strategies, provide good and fair working environment and promote work life balance mechanism to increase job satisfaction and there by employee productivity and morale. Also, they suggest that removing all that work place stress is essential for sustainment of the employees and organisational commitment

Dr. Resmi R and Dr. Suramya Mathai [2021], in their study highlights the dimensions of job-related stress and satisfaction based on their socio-economic variables like marital status, educational qualification and employment status of the spouse. The findings of the study show that single employees experience more levels of job-related stress than compared to married persons. The study concludes that job satisfaction and stress are some way related but job satisfaction cannot be considered as an effective tool for reducing the work-related stress. Also, the authors point out the importance of implementation of stress management strategies and new innovative HR practices to enhance employee well-being and retention.

VII. METHODOLOGY

The study uses a quantitative research design to analyse the impact of work stress and job satisfaction on employee job satisfaction among IT employees. The population consists of IT employees working in various companies in Ernakulam city from which 58 respondents were mailed through google doc questionnaire and a final 50 respondents were selected. Primary data is collected through structure questionnaire to capture the respondent's opinion accurately. The collected data is analysed using statistical tools such as percentage analysis, mean and chi-square test analysis. Descriptive statistics are used to summarise the demographic information related to age, gender, marital status and years of experience.

TESTING HYPOTHESIS

- **H01:** There is no significant relationship between works related factors (workload, long working hours, role ambiguity, and work-life imbalance) and professional burnout among IT employees.

VIII. RESULT ANALYSIS

Table I: Comparison of Work-related factors

Sl No	Attributes	Yes	No	Total
1	Workload	20	5	25
2	Long working hours	15	3	18
3	Role ambiguity	4	6	10
4	Work life imbalance	3	4	7
	Total	42	18	60

$$\text{Chi-square} = \sum (O-E)^2 / E$$

Table II: Computation of Chi-square value

Attributes	O	E	O-E	(O-E) ² /E
Workload (Yes)	20	17.50	2.50	0.36
Long Working hours (Yes)	15	12.60	2.40	0.46
Role ambiguity (Yes)	4	7	3	1.29
Work life Imbalance (Yes)	3	4.90	1.90	0.74
Workload (No)	5	7.50	2.50	0.83
Long Working hours (No)	3	5.40	2.40	1.07
Role ambiguity (No)	6	3	3	3
Work life Imbalance (No)	4	2.10	1.90	1.72
Total				9.47

df=3

LOS=.05

Table value = 7.815

Decision

Here the Table value is less than the calculated value. So we reject the null hypothesis and conclude there is a relation between work related factors like work load, long hours of work and work life will lead to professional burnout among IT employees.

- **H02:** Work pressure has no significant impact on job satisfaction among IT employees.

Table III: Computation of Work Pressure on Job satisfaction

Work Pressure	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Total
Low	18	4	3	25
Moderate	6	8	6	20
High	2	5	8	15
Total	26	17	17	60

Here Expected frequencies = Row total x Colomn total / Grand total

Table IV: Computation of Chi-square value

Here df=4

Attributes	O	E	(O-E) ² /E
Low (Satisfied)	18	10.83	4.75
Low (Neutral)	4	7.08	1.34
Low (Dissatisfied)	3	7.08	2.35
Moderate (Satisfied)	6	8.67	.82
Moderate (Neutral)	8	5.67	0.96
Moderate (Dissatisfied)	6	5.67	0.02
High (Satisfied)	2	6.50	3.12
High (Neutral)	5	4.25	0.13
High (Dissatisfied)	8	4.25	3.31
Total			16.8

Table value=9.488

Decision

Calculated value s more than table value. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and accept and found that there is a significant relationship with work pressure and Job satisfaction.

IX. CONCLUSION

The study found that work stress and Job burn out negatively affect the employee Job satisfaction. Those employees having higher level of work stress report higher level of dissatisfaction compared with lower work-related stress. Also increased work demands, project deadlines, continuous screen time all will affect the employee personal well-being which adversely contribute to decreased Job satisfaction. As these stress levels and professional burnout rises it affect the employee commitment and productivity. Therefore, the management should give attention to implement new strategies that will reduce those work-related matters for the overall benefit of the organisation.

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